

MS5 UC collections characterize d for traits of interest

Lead Beneficiary: P6 (CSIC)

Milestone Description & Contributors

- **Due date:** 30/04/2025
- **Actual submission date:** 30/04/2025
- **Project start date:** September 1st 2021
- **Duration:** 48 months
- **Work package:** WP2
- **Work package leader:** Diego Rubiales
- **Milestone Title:** UC collections characterized for traits of interest

- **Mean of Verification**

As described in the Grant Agreement, section 1.3.4 - A phenotyping database for traits of interest (yield stability, stress resistance, nutritional, health-promoting) will be produced.

Such database was produced and distributed to partners which are using it to gather all characterizations data, activity which is still ongoing for some crops in some locations. The database will be updated in D2.3.

1. Milestone description

A phenotyping database for traits of interest has been built and distributed to partners which are using it to gather all characterizations data, activity which is still ongoing for some crops in some locations.

Complementing EU CropStore EU_CropStore _input template workbook_10_1_Radiant_2022a.xlsx, MS5 generated a user friendly excel file, composed with as many sheets as crops covered (i.e. in alphabetical order: sheet 1 aniseed; sheet 2 annual medics; sheet 3 bambara; sheet 4 cowpea; sheet 5 common vetch; sheet 6 faba bean; sheet 7 foxtail millet; sheet 8 lentil; sheet 9 pea; sheet 10 sesame; sheet 11 soybean; sheet 12 tomato; sheet 13 Vicia ervilia; sheet 14 Vicia narbonensis; sheet 15 and sho on).

The size of each sheet varies as do the numbers of accessions characterized for each crop (i.e. from a few dozens in the case of annual medics, aniseed or tomato, to a few hundred in the case of faba bean and many others) as well as the numbers of seasons (i.e. only one season for sesame to three seasons in the case of faba bean and others), as the numbers of accessed traits. Therefore, each sheet contains a variable number of columns, being in common:

Column 1: accession code

Column 2: synonym (donor code)

Column 3: location

Column 4: season

Column 5: rep

Column 6: trait 1, i.e. day to flowering

Column 7: trait 2, i.e. flower colour

Column 8: trait 3, i.e. plant stature

Column 9: trait 4, i.e. podding date

Column 10: trait 5, i.e. pod or fruit shape

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Column 11: trait 6, i.e. pod or fruit color

Column 12: trait 7, i.e. pod or fruit size

Column 13: trait 8, i.e. yield

Column 14: trait 9, i.e. incidence of pests

Column 15: trait 10, i.e. incidence of diseases

Column 16: trait 11, i.e. quality traits if accessed

Column x-y: as many specific traits accessed for each specific crop

2. Mean of Verification

Have you provided the Mean of Verification described in the GA? Yes

If Yes: **Template excel** file with an example sheet as follows, with as many sheets as crops covered.

identification		traits accessed																
plant species	accession code	synonym	origin	testing site	season	rep	trait 1, i.e. day to flowering	trait 2, i.e. flower colour	trait 3, i.e. plant stature	trait 4, i.e. podding date	trait 5, i.e. pod or fruit shape	trait 6, i.e. pod or fruit color	trait 7, i.e. pod or fruit size	trait 8, i.e. yield	trait 9, i.e. incidence of pests	trait 10, i.e. incidence of diseases	trait 11, i.e. quality traits if accessed	Column x-y: as many specific traits accessed for each specific crop
Pisum sativum	PA 0001	HBG01058	Croatia	site 1	season 1	1												
Pisum sativum	PA 0001	HBG01058	Croatia	site 1	season 1	2												
Pisum sativum	PA 0001	HBG01058	Croatia	site 1	season 1	3												
Pisum sativum	PA 0001	HBG01058	Croatia	site 2	season 1	1												
Pisum sativum	PA 0001	HBG01058	Croatia	site 2	season 1	2												
Pisum sativum	PA 0001	HBG01058	Croatia	site 2	season 1	3												
Pisum sativum	PA 0001	HBG01058	Croatia	site 1	season 2	1												
Pisum sativum	PA 0001	HBG01058	Croatia	site 1	season 2	2												
Pisum sativum	PA 0001	HBG01058	Croatia	site 1	season 2	3												
Pisum sativum	PA 0001	HBG01058	Croatia	site 2	season 2	1												
Pisum sativum	PA 0001	HBG01058	Croatia	site 2	season 2	2												
Pisum sativum	PA 0001	HBG01058	Croatia	site 2	season 2	3												
Pisum sativum	PA 0003	HBG00402	Italia	site 1	season 1	1												
Pisum sativum	PA 0003	HBG00402	Italia	site 1	season 1	2												
Pisum sativum	PA 0003	HBG00402	Italia	site 1	season 1	3												
Pisum sativum	PA 0003	HBG00402	Italia	site 2	season 1	1												
Pisum sativum	PA 0003	HBG00402	Italia	site 2	season 1	2												
Pisum sativum	PA 0003	HBG00402	Italia	site 2	season 1	3												
Pisum sativum	PA 0003	HBG00402	Italia	site 1	season 2	1												
Pisum sativum	PA 0003	HBG00402	Italia	site 1	season 2	2												
Pisum sativum	PA 0003	HBG00402	Italia	site 1	season 2	3												
Pisum sativum	PA 0003	HBG00402	Italia	site 2	season 2	1												
Pisum sativum	PA 0003	HBG00402	Italia	site 2	season 2	2												
Pisum sativum	PA 0003	HBG00402	Italia	site 2	season 2	3												
Pisum sativum	PA 0032	AMES27782	Paestina	site 1	season 1	1												
Pisum sativum	PA 0032	AMES27782	Paestina	site 1	season 1	2												
Pisum sativum	PA 0032	AMES27782	Paestina	site 1	season 1	3												
Pisum sativum	PA 0032	AMES27782	Paestina	site 2	season 1	1												
Pisum sativum	PA 0032	AMES27782	Paestina	site 2	season 1	2												
Pisum sativum	PA 0032	AMES27782	Paestina	site 2	season 1	3												
Pisum sativum	PA 0032	AMES27782	Paestina	site 1	season 2	1												
Pisum sativum	PA 0032	AMES27782	Paestina	site 1	season 2	2												
Pisum sativum	PA 0032	AMES27782	Paestina	site 1	season 2	3												
Pisum sativum	PA 0032	AMES27782	Paestina	site 2	season 2	1												
Pisum sativum	PA 0032	AMES27782	Paestina	site 2	season 2	2												
Pisum sativum	PA 0032	AMES27782	Paestina	site 2	season 2	3												
Pisum sativum	x	x	x	site 1	season 1	1												
Pisum sativum	x	x	x	site 1	season 1	2												
Pisum sativum	x	x	x	site 1	season 1	3												
Pisum sativum	x	x	x	site 2	season 1	1												
Pisum sativum	x	x	x	site 2	season 1	2												
Pisum sativum	x	x	x	site 2	season 1	3												
Pisum sativum	x	x	x	site 1	season 2	1												
Pisum sativum	x	x	x	site 1	season 2	2												
Pisum sativum	x	x	x	site 1	season 2	3												
Pisum sativum	x	x	x	site 2	season 2	1												
Pisum sativum	x	x	x	site 2	season 2	2												
Pisum sativum	x	x	x	site 2	season 2	3												
Pisum sativum	y	y	y	site 1	season 1	1												
Pisum sativum	y	y	y	site 1	season 1	2												
Pisum sativum	y	y	y	site 1	season 1	3												
Pisum sativum	y	y	y	site 2	season 1	1												
Pisum sativum	y	y	y	site 2	season 1	2												
Pisum sativum	y	y	y	site 2	season 1	3												
Pisum sativum	y	y	y	site 1	season 2	1												
Pisum sativum	y	y	y	site 1	season 2	2												
Pisum sativum	y	y	y	site 1	season 2	3												
Pisum sativum	y	y	y	site 2	season 2	1												
Pisum sativum	y	y	y	site 2	season 2	2												
Pisum sativum	y	y	y	site 2	season 2	3												
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